

The Importance of Didactics in Pedagogy and Stages of The Didactic Process

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Abstract

The specific content of the article examines the specific tasks of the methodology for professional training of students in the vocational education system.

Keyword: professional training, vocational education system, methodology, methods, teacher styles.

INTRODUCTION

The methodology of professional training is formed and developed on the basis of in-depth analysis and generalization of advanced pedagogical experience as a branch of pedagogical knowledge and a subject of study. From a scientific point of view, the methodology of vocational education is a private didactics and is based on professional pedagogy, educational psychology and physiology, which reveal the patterns of knowledge acquisition, the formation of skills and competencies. The general issues of the vocational training process, characteristic of the practical vocational training of qualified specialists in any field, the basis for the implementation of the process of practical vocational training in specific professions, the basis for the preparation of private teaching methods are revealed. The methodology of vocational education, which is part of the psychological and pedagogical sciences, occupies one of the leading places in the training of vocational education teachers. This makes it possible to prepare future teachers for methodologically competent and creative implementation of the pedagogical process in vocational educational institutions. The distinctive features of this disciplinary structure are the content and procedural components. The content component provides didactic, diagnostic, and conceptual components. Intellectual activity of students and teachers in acquiring and mastering procedural knowledge and skills, as well as managing this process.

Research materials. Today, the methodology of vocational education is developing in two main directions. The first is related to the development of the methodology of professional training, the second is the relatively independent development of special methods used in the study of technical sciences: technical mathematics, drawing, electrical engineering, etc. Methodological knowledge is related to methods and techniques, as well as the teacher's own personality and creative approach. Vocational education methodology considers the process of teaching a particular subject in an educational institution as its object of knowledge. The subject of knowledge is pedagogical knowledge and design skills, the use of such educational tools that help organize the educational activities of the teacher and the development and acquisition of professional knowledge by students, as well as the ability to apply this knowledge in practice. . The objects of knowledge of technical

sciences are technical systems and devices, but the methodology of professional training is this studying systems and devices does not set itself the task of forming methods of studying them. His object of knowledge is the very process of social education and upbringing with the help of the studied science.

The methodology of vocational education is an important component of the professional training of teachers in vocational schools. Methodological knowledge serves the professional activities of vocational school teachers and is closely related to the methods of this activity and, of course, to the teacher himself and his activities. In order to provide a system of theoretical knowledge on the methodology of vocational training, it is necessary to construct an object, topic, conceptual and terminological apparatus, and determine methods for studying the work practice of teachers. The object of knowledge of the methodology of professional education is the process of teaching a certain subject in an educational institution (for example, if we talk about the methodology of teaching design, then the object of methodological knowledge of design is the study of the “learning process”), i.e. the goals of studying this subject, the content of the program, methods and forms of organizing educational and cognitive activities of students, educational results). At the same time, the learning process is the object of study of the pedagogy of vocational education. The set of objects of knowledge of methodology and pedagogy represents a single methodological and pedagogical knowledge.

shows a feature. However, what is the difference between methodology and pedagogy? The differences between teaching methods and pedagogy should be sought in the nature of the teacher’s pedagogical activity as a teacher of a specific subject and as a teacher who combines methodological activity in his teaching activity (which, of course, is interdependent). The subject of activity of a teacher of a specific subject - the organization of the educational process in this subject - is shown in Figure 1. The teacher organizes the cognitive (educational) activities of students based on the content and teaching methods. The result of educational activities is a prepared student, his system of professional knowledge and skills, developed personal and professional abilities.

Research result. At the same time, the teacher, in order to form new knowledge and skills in his professional activities, natural science teachers and students as an interaction of actions. Interactions can be planned and organized using specially designed tools used in training. In a broad sense, teaching aids optimize the learning process in a subject and ensure the achievement of planned learning outcomes in the lesson. Consequently, the result of methodological activities are specially designed educational tools that form a “channel” through which the teacher’s educational activities are carried out and students acquire professional knowledge, skills and competencies cognitive activity is regulated. The main direction of pedagogy is dialectical unity, interdependence, unification of the structural elements of the educational process. The methodology is dominated by the questions: “how to teach?”, “with the help of what teaching tools will the content of education be transformed into the knowledge and skills of students?”

Conclusion. The presence of methodological knowledge ensures effective professional activity of the teacher. They are closely related to the ways and means of this activity, as well as to the individual typological characteristics of the teacher, his level of qualifications, life and pedagogical experience and intuition. Characterizing these fundamentals, it can be noted that the choice of methodology should be based on the nature of the academic discipline. In addition, it is based on studying the history of the development of the relevant field of knowledge, defining the mission of the educational institution, modern achievements in the field of pedagogy, psychology, sociology and other sciences, and there must be comprehensive knowledge about the intellectual capabilities of

students and their age-related characteristics and how these characteristics are manifested in these specific conditions.

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